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DELIVERABLE REPORT

SUPERCRITICAL CO₂ AS A REFRIGERANT

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Abstract:

The present deliverable documents the achievement of Task 10.4 towards a universal adoption of natural refrigerants for future generations of detectors, covering in particular situations where water or boiling CO₂ flows cannot be used. The programme announced in the submitted proposal has been extended thanks to synergies with internal funds to the case of ultra-cold detectors, requiring operation below the limit temperatures achievable with boiling CO₂. Two natural fluids have been considered: supercritical carbon dioxide and Krypton. Based on the outcome of scientific literature review and theoretical studies, two new dedicated test setups have been designed, built and launched in operation.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

The use of refrigerants with low environmental impact is becoming an imperative for all refrigeration and thermal management applications. Research infrastructures should not only adapt to the new legislation, but also show the example and pave the way to the adoption of virtuous behaviours in the industry. Replacing synthetic fluids by natural refrigerants is by far the most effective way to minimize the environmental footprint of cooling systems, and this can be done without compromising, or even enhancing, the technical performances. The present deliverable presents the progress achieved in the frame of the AIDAinnova project towards the possibility of extending the use of natural refrigerants for detector cooling to cases where, until now, the choice of synthetic refrigerants was considered unavoidable.

The first case refers to the use of carbon dioxide above its critical point (supercritical CO₂, or sCO₂) for all applications where the radiation level is low and the detectors can be operated at warm temperatures. In these cases, water – the most used natural refrigerant – is a good choice, but its electrical conductivity is a danger for the detector electronics and synthetic dielectric refrigerants are often preferred. If the electronics can operate at temperatures in the range 31 to 45 °C, which is usually the case, sCO₂ provides an excellent alternative, with a benefit of superior thermo-fluidic properties as compared to water, allowing with smaller pipes and more compact and efficient systems. However, the scientific literature on the properties of sCO₂ as refrigerant is still very scattered and evident contradiction between published data prevent to establish reliable models for the designers of the future cooling systems. For this reason, a dedicated experimental setup has been designed and put in operation.

The second case was foreseen from the beginning for Task 10.4 but was removed from the proposal to optimize the budget. However, it has been possible to recuperate it thanks to the synergy with an internal R&D programme funded by CERN and NTNU. It refers to the use of Krypton for applications where, on the other hand, the detectors are exposed to radiation levels higher than the one reached during the first phase of HL-LHC (Run 4), and avoiding thermal runaway will require lower temperatures than the one achievable by CO₂ boiling flows. For temperatures below -50 °C there is presently no valid alternative fluid with low environmental impact to the universally adopted synthetic refrigerants like R23 (CHF₃), and for this reason the use of such fluids is still allowed by the European directives. Studies conducted at CERN and NTNU demonstrate that Krypton, a natural gas with GWP of 0.335, has even superior properties to those of R23 and can be conveniently used for detector cooling down to temperatures well below -80 °C. An innovative ejector-based refrigeration cycle was designed and a first prototype was tested with positive results.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of refrigerants with low environmental impact is becoming an imperative for all refrigeration and thermal management applications. Research infrastructures should not only adapt to the new legislation progressively enforced by EU, but must also show the example and pave the way to the adoption of virtuous behaviours in the industry. Replacing synthetic fluids by natural refrigerants is by far the most effective way to minimize the environmental footprint of cooling systems, and this can be done without compromising, or actually even enhancing, the technical performances.

Beside water – by far the most widely used refrigerant in standard applications – Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) have been for a long time in use in the refrigeration industry since the

discovery of the high Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP) of the first generation of synthetic refrigerants in the Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and Hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs) classes. For the thermal management of critical detectors, where the use of water with or without freezing point depressants requires too large diameter pipes and is too dangerous for the electronics in case of leaks, Perfluorocarbons (PFCs) have been adopted due to their resistance to high ionising radiation doses. However, both HFCs and PFCs have been shown to exhibit a very high Global Warming Potential (GWP) and are being progressively phased-out following the adoption of the Kigali amendment to the Montreal protocol in 2016. The reaction of the chemical industry has been the introduction in the market of a new generation of synthetic refrigerants, the Hydrofluoroolefins (HFOs) and the Hydrofluoroethers (HFEs). Further than being less resistant to ionizing radiations than PFCs, and therefore only marginally useful for detector applications, these new refrigerants have been recently proven to be a source of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs), a large class of chemicals extremely persistent in the environment and proven to have harmful effects on humans. EU is progressively issuing new regulations restricting the use of PFAS-producing fluids.

The very positive experience with boiling carbon dioxide (CO₂) flows for the thermal management of vertex detectors in the present generation of LHC experiments, paved the way to the generalized extension of this technology to all cold-operated semiconductor detectors for the first phase of HL-LHC (Run 4). In this context, it has been decided to include in AIDAinnova a Task finalized at fostering the universal adoption of natural refrigerants for future generations of detectors, individuating natural fluids that can be conveniently used in future detectors in all case where:

- the use of water is not possible or has strong contraindications;
- the required operational temperature is outside the limit of operation of the present CO₂ systems (-43 °C to + 20 °C).

Considering that, among natural fluids, it is highly preferable to avoid flammable gases, like those belonging to the Hydrocarbons class (HC), or highly toxic gases like Ammonia (NH₃), two fluids have been considered

- Supercritical carbon dioxide (sCO₂) for detectors that do not require low operational temperatures;
- Krypton (Kr) for detectors exposed to very high radiation levels and requiring operational temperatures below -50 °C.

It may be noted that the study of Krypton as refrigerant for ultra-cold detectors was not included in the submitted AIDAinnova proposal. This line of research was anyway present in the initial draft, but was cut due to budget constraints. However, thanks to synergies with parallel lines of R&D financed by internal funds from the two institutes in charge of Task 10.4 (NTNU and CERN), it has been possible to recover this activity within the programme of WP10 after the approval of the AIDAinnova project.

Indeed there are strong links between the two activities, in particular since the innovative refrigeration cycle developed for Kr (see section 3) operates for an important part in the supercritical state, in conditions (reduced pressure p_r in the order of 1.2) very similar to those that can be now extensively explored on sCO₂ with the new dedicated test bench (see section 2).

2. SUPERCRITICAL CARBON DIOXIDE

2.1. PROPERTIES OF SCO₂ AS REFRIGERANT

High thermal capacities and low values of density and viscosity are some of the main characteristics of fluids above their critical point. Furthermore, thanks to their inherent single-phase-like nature, supercritical fluids allow for a relatively simple fluid dynamic management in multibranch circuits. Supercritical CO₂ is in particular very promising for warm temperature cooling applications, due to its distinctive thermophysical behaviour near the pseudo-critical point. Above the critical pressure of 7.4 MPa and critical temperature of 31 °C, CO₂ enters the supercritical region, where it no longer has distinct liquid or vapor phases. Figure 1 shows the variation of several important thermophysical and transport properties.

Figure 1: variation of several important thermophysical and transport properties of sCO₂ with temperature and pressure: a) heat capacity; b) density; c) thermal conductivity; d) dynamic viscosity

In this region, the isobaric specific heat capacity (C_p , Figure 1.a) exhibits a pronounced peak at the pseudo-critical temperature, enhancing the fluid's capacity to absorb thermal energy. The temperature at which the C_p reaches a maximum point is called the pseudocritical point. As the system pressure increases, the magnitude of this maximum decreases and the parabolic shape widens, thus extending the temperature range over which a high heat capacity is sustained—an advantageous feature for systems operating near ambient temperatures. In addition to the C_p behaviour, steep variations in thermal conductivity (Figure 1.b) and density (Figure 1.c) near the pseudo-critical point significantly affect convective heat transfer. Figure 1.d also shows the variation of the dynamic

viscosity with temperature at different pressures. The heat transfer coefficient in forced convection scales with the product of thermal conductivity and the Nusselt number, the latter of which is dependent on density-driven changes in flow behaviour. Near the pseudocritical point, the sharp density gradients could enhance buoyancy-driven secondary flows and promote turbulence, as well as a reduced dynamic viscosity. These effects could lead to enhanced convective heat transfer performance compared to conventional single-phase fluids, making supercritical CO₂ an excellent working fluid for compact, high-efficiency thermal management systems.

In comparison, water—with high heat capacity and thermal conductivity—exhibits relatively stable properties with temperature and significantly higher viscosity, limiting its convective performance in single-phase flow under similar conditions. As an example, Figure 2 compares some key parameters calculated at 33 °C and 80 bar for various mass flow rates of sCO₂, water and R134a (a synthetic fluid widely used as refrigerant for room temperature applications) flowing in a 1 m-long pipe of inner diameter 1 mm, where a uniform heat of 200 W is dissipated. It can be noticed that sCO₂ exhibits a higher heat transfer coefficient than water, with significantly lower pressure drops and a reduced temperature glide along the heat exchanger (pipe).

Figure 2: variation of several important thermophysical and transport properties of sCO₂ with mass flux and pressure: a) heat capacity; b) density; c) thermal conductivity; d) dynamic viscosity (simulation at $T = 33\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p = 80\text{ bar}$)

2.2. STUDIES ON SCO₂ HEAT TRANSFER IN LITERATURE

In modern electronics, and particularly in High Energy Physics (HEP) detectors, efficient thermal management is critical to ensure reliability and performance throughout the entire lifetime of the detector. The demand for compact, high-power devices poses significant challenges to thermal engineers. Additionally, the need for environmentally low-impact refrigerants has become increasingly important due to stringent regulations. While boiling CO₂ is well-established at CERN for applications requiring low temperatures, the use of supercritical CO₂ (sCO₂) offers unique potential for the thermal management of electronic components that can be operated above its critical temperature (31 °C). With its high specific heat capacity, low viscosity, and single-phase behaviour, sCO₂ presents a simplified alternative with comparable performances to boiling CO₂ in the warm domain.

However, density, heat capacity and thermal conductivity of sCO₂ vary sharply in the region around the pseudocritical¹ point. As a direct consequence, the heat transfer properties of sCO₂ are not yet fully characterized, nor understood. Precise values of heat transfer coefficient, as well as pressure drops are not widely available in the available scientific literature, especially when reaching inner diameters smaller than 4 mm.

The primary focus of studying the heat transfer behaviour of sCO₂ lied until now in its applications for power systems and related fields. Other articles find their motivation in studying sCO₂ as a modelling fluid for application in nuclear reactor cooling with supercritical water. Little can still be found in literature directly addressing electronics cooling, despite this being clearly an emerging area with significant potential. Fronk et al. [1] and Stottlemire et al. [2] addressed this topic: in [1], a 1D model of a representative 15mmx15mm silicon heat sink with 25 parallel square microchannels with hydraulic diameter (D_h) equal to 0.5mm was developed. The performance of sCO₂ was compared to that of single-phase water and FC-72, and two-phase R-134a. The authors concluded that sCO₂ shows clear advantages due to its high volumetric thermal capacity near the pseudocritical temperature, but the uncertainties related to the existing heat transfer models under high heat fluxes and microscale conditions limited the accurate prediction of sCO₂ performance. They also highlighted the need for further research to develop more reliable and validated models. In [2], the authors reported heat transfer coefficients (HTC) up to 50 kW/m²K in a cold plate containing eight parallel microchannels with dimensions 1.38 mm x 1.02 mm (WxH). Data were acquired at constant inlet conditions equal to 80 bar and 34.1 °C. They emphasized that the use of sCO₂ as a coolant for electronics applications would largely benefit from further precision measurements of the HTC with different operating pressures.

Broader studies on heat transfer and heat transfer characterization provide significantly more information regarding the trends of the main parameters affecting the system performance (operating pressure, diameter, mass flux, heat flux, inlet temperature and flow orientation) and are summarized in this section. However, as stated previously, only a limited number of research articles investigate diameters below 4 mm diameter.

The only parameter affecting heat transfer with sCO₂ where authors have reached a uniform conclusion has been the operating pressure. The main role of operating pressure is the dampening of the variation in physical properties like the heat capacity – which directly affects the maximum heat transfer coefficient attainable – while keeping other parameters constant. As the operating pressure has a dampening effect on the extreme variation of the thermodynamic and transport properties, the HTC follows the same trend. This means that the sharp increase observed when approaching the pseudocritical point by means of changing the fluid temperature becomes less drastic when increasing the operating pressure, while keeping other parameters constant. References [3] and [4] contain further information on the effect of pressure.

The effect of varying diameter remains poorly documented, especially at inner diameters below 2 mm, where only two studies provided insights regarding the effect of the pipe size (in heating experiments). Liao and Zhao [5] observed that the Nusselt number and heat transfer coefficients increased when increasing the diameter at equal values of flow velocity in their sCO₂ heating studies at 80 bar operating pressure. They measured in pipes with diameters ranging from 0.7 to 2.16 mm.

¹ For fluids in supercritical conditions, i.e. at pressure and temperature above the values of the critical point, the “pseudocritical point” is the point corresponding to the maximum value of the specific heat at each particular pressure.

For their study, they kept the ratio m/D constant as well as the fluid inlet conditions, and subsequently constant Reynolds and Prandtl numbers. For their experiments, the Reynolds number was always above 10^4 . They compared their results with the Dittus-Boelter correlation and concluded that at their conditions, higher diameters led to higher Nusselt numbers. They attributed this effect to the influence of buoyancy in the overall heat transfer mechanism. For this, they used the Buoyancy parameter (Gr/Re^2), although the threshold they set for buoyancy to be considered negligible was much lower (three orders of magnitude) than the common value used for this analysis and the source of this threshold was not easily available in the open literature. It is possible that this parameter has a much smaller value in supercritical fluids than in conventional single phase, considering that it is strongly dependant on the thermal expansion coefficient, which can change rapidly in the supercritical region. Although their results were interesting, they did not provide further analysis regarding the main role of buoyancy in the heated fluid flow. Additionally, showing their results at different tube sizes with different operating pressures could have provided further insights on the influence of the thermal expansion coefficient or, more broadly, of the dimensionless buoyancy parameter.

In the second research article by Wang et al. [6], the authors found higher heat transfer coefficients at smaller pipe diameter in their studies carried out at similar diameters (0.5 to 1.0 mm) and almost equal pressure conditions (80.5 bar outer pressure), with only the tube inlet temperature being significantly different and much closer to the pseudocritical point in this case. The values they obtained for the HTC in the tube with 1.0 mm inner diameter flowing 1.67 g/s was six times lower than what Liao and Zhao found in their 1.4 mm tube with a mass flow of 1.11 g/s. In addition, their conclusion for the effect of the tube diameter on the heat transfer coefficient was the complete opposite. Ehsan et al. [7] commented on this discrepancy and highlighted the different results obtained by several authors.

The effect of varying the mass flux has brought discrepancies in the literature with vertical up-flow. Three different studies [8], [9], [10] performed sCO₂ heating experiments in vertical upward flow. The diameters ranged from 4 to 22 mm and q/G conditions were similar. They defined a threshold to discern between low and high mass flow domains, since the results showed big differences in heat transfer coefficients between those conditions. In the low mass flow domain, they reported that higher mass flows lead to a reduction in the HTC, whereas in the high mass flow domain, the trend was the opposite. Peng et al. [10] and Zhang et al. [8] defined a threshold for the low mass flow domain at similar values of mass flux (respectively 200 and 300 kg/m²s). They justified this difference in trend to be due to the contribution of both forced and natural convection in the overall heat transfer process. On the other hand, Zahlan et al. [11] found the general trend to be homogeneous for all their mass fluxes, where higher mass fluxes lead to higher HTC. Similarly, for horizontal and downward flows, three articles reported the same trend [12], [6], [13]. These articles studied HTC in lower diameter conditions (between 1 and 4 mm).

Finally, the main point of discrepancy in literature was found to be the effect of the heat flux on the HTC and the appearance of a critical heat flux, a value from which the heat transfer of the fluid can be defined as impaired (Heat Transfer Deterioration or HTD). Impaired heat transfer refers, in this context, to the appearance of a peak in wall temperature, which corresponds to a local minimum heat transfer coefficient. Many authors have developed correlations solely based on the ratio q/G to study the effect of the heat flux in the HTC and appearance of HTD. However, in the extensive study from Kurganov et al. [14], [15], [16], [17] six different typical groups of deteriorated heat transfer regimes were distinguished based on the ratio of hydrostatic resistance coefficient and friction coefficient at the pipe inlet. Specifically, in [14], the regimes were phenomenologically described.

They pointed out that one of the main difficulties in generalizing the experimental data on HTD regimes was the strong dependence of the local heat transfer on the previous history of the process. What they meant by this was that the curves obtained at different h_{in} had individual patterns and coincided with one another only at $h_b \approx h_{m1}$ or more, being h_{m1} the specific enthalpy value at which the fluid could be considered a gas, based on the value of the relative work of expansion of the fluid. More information on this parameter can be found in their research article, as well as a short summary in [18].

In the study of Kline et al. [19] the authors noted for the first time that there was a range of temperature values for which HTD occurred for each diameter, mass flux and heat flux. More recently, Zhu et al. [20], demonstrated HTD occurrence at different inlet temperatures while keeping other parameters fixed, showing that a simple correlation based on the ratio q/G was not enough to explain the appearance of temperature peaks along the pipe.

Finally, there are not many studies showing the transition from near-critical boiling to near-critical supercritical flow. Only the research article from Lei et al. [21] focused on this topic and highlighted that the differences between subcritical and supercritical pressures had rarely been tested and analysed in detail.

Considering this to be the current state of the field of heat transfer studies in sCO₂ experiments, it is imperative to focus on defining and characterizing the process in a systematic manner. Indeed, the available data are very scattered, which makes the extraction of general trends extremely difficult. For this reason, a dedicated experimental setup at CERN was planned and built, with the goal of exploring the sCO₂ heated flow and systematically evaluating the influencing parameters. This study is part of a PhD thesis, which is planned to be finalized this year. This thesis will be publicly available and will include a literature review with over 60 referenced articles. For this deliverable document and this shortened version of the literature analysis, the main aspects of sCO₂ flow have been evaluated and a summary, including the main aspects to be determined during the exploitation of the test facility, is presented below:

Effect of diameter at different pressures: as there seem to be published studies reporting uncanny trends of the heat transfer coefficient when heating sCO₂ at different tube diameters at constant inlet conditions and horizontal flow, one of the first priorities of our tests will be to systematically measure and analyse the influence of tube diameter on heat transfer performance. In this context, heat transfer performance refers to the HTC and its variation along the flow path, together with the pressure drop across the heated section. Special emphasis will be placed on identifying the role of buoyancy effects in the observed heat transfer behaviour in pipes with diameters below 3 mm. Given the strong dependence of buoyancy-driven flows on the fluid's thermal characteristics, particular attention will be given to evaluating the effect of the pipe diameter and the buoyancy parameter on the heat transfer coefficient at different operating pressures.

Effect of mass flux in vertical up-flow: The existence of a threshold value for the mass flux in a heated pipe with sCO₂ vertical flow, where the trend of the heat transfer coefficient with respect to the flow velocity showed a reversal, suggests that both forced and natural convection contribute to the overall heat transfer process. However, discrepancies in the literature indicate that this threshold might not be universal and could depend on more specific flow conditions. To clarify these inconsistencies, the effect of mass flux on heat transfer in vertical sCO₂ flow will be studied, particularly in small-diameter pipes.

Heat Transfer Deterioration (HTD): The occurrence of HTD in sCO₂ flows remains a complex and debated topic, as different studies report varying mechanisms and thresholds for its

onset. While many authors have attempted to correlate HTD with the heat flux-to-mass flux ratio, more detailed studies have suggested that multiple interacting parameters play a critical role, as specified earlier in this section. Given these discrepancies and the complexity of the phenomenon, a systematic approach is needed to better define and predict HTD under different operating conditions.

Sub-critical near-critical studies: as direct comparisons of the near-critical below and above- critical point heat transfer performances are scarce in literature, the study will aim to provide an analysis of heat transfer behaviour in these regions. By investigating the transition across the critical point, this work will help clarify the underlying mechanisms influencing heat transfer performance and identify key parameters that govern these changes.

2.3. THE NEW DEDICATED TEST RIG BUILT AT CERN

The test rig was designed from scratch to cope with a maximum of the existing open points in literature, in the ranges of interest typical of detector electronic cooling. It was finally commissioned in January 2025 and started its operation in February 2025. It consists of a closed pumped loop, where the main unit is the hydraulic accumulator (AC-101 in the P&ID). The unit was designed by the manufacturer HYDAC to fit this test setup specifically. Figure 3 shows the front view of the test rig. The following description can be followed with Figure 8, reporting the P&ID.

Carbon dioxide is pressurized in this unit by means of a piston, where nitrogen is used as the pressurizing agent. The accumulator consists of two separate units: the bellow section and the piston section. The piston section contains nitrogen gas, which compresses the bellow section to pressurize the system fluid.

Figure 3: Front view of the test rig

AC-101 serves as the setpoint control for the entire rig, with an operating envelope ranging from 50 to 120 bar. To ensure enough subcooling before sending the fluid to liquid pump (LP101) when studying near-critical boiling, the accumulator is equipped with a custom cooling coil around.

Figure 4 shows the accumulator unit, the cooling coil, the nitrogen lines and the cooling unit.

After AC101, the fluid is pumped through the rest of the system by means of a magnetically driven rotary vane pump LP101, M-PUMPS VA MODULAR 25. To protect downstream components, a filtering system is installed immediately after the pump (LEWA Inline-Filter F-MI2-I-s-f4 3). This system removes possible debris in the flow, in particular those originating from progressive wearing of the pump vanes. Subsequently, a first rough flow regulation is installed, which consists of a simple bypass valve (Swagelok SS-20VS4). The remaining flow passes through a Coriolis mass-flow meter (RHEONIK RHM02 with RHE45), and a micrometric regulation valve (Swagelok SS-1RS6MM) is installed for more precise flow control. After the second flow regulation, the fluid temperature is regulated by means of the electric heater (EH101), where the desired temperature of the test section can be achieved (WATLOW CAST X-500).

Figure 4: The accumulator (AC101) with the cooling coil and nitrogen lines. The chiller (CU101) is visible in the back.

Once heated, the fluid enters the test section, and its pressure and temperature are measured (PT106, TT106). The fluid then flows through the test section: in the present configuration this has an inner diameter of 1 mm and an outer diameter of 1.59 mm. The test section has a length of 1 meter and heating is provided to it through electrodes, by means of resistive heating. To suppress parasitic current dispersion through the metal piping and delimit the heated length, the supply of the heater is placed in the middle of the test section, while the ground and negative sides are located in the extremities of the pipe. Additionally, a flow developing length (adiabatic) is allowed at the entrance of the pipe, with a length equal to $L/D = 50$. In this case, 50 mm. The power is supplied to the test section by means of a DC power supply (Delta Electronika SM15-100). Due to the low resistance of the pipe, high currents and low voltages are needed. The wall temperature along the test section is measured with 10 equally spaced K-type thermocouples, installed throughout the whole pipe length, ensuring direct contact with the outer wall of the tube. In the outlet of the test section, temperature and differential pressure sensors are installed (DP101, TT107). Finally, before and after the test section, dielectric fittings are installed to avoid any current leakage to the rest of the system. The pressure measurement lines are equipped with a small PEEK section for the same purpose. Figure 5 shows the presently installed test section.

Figure 5: Top view of the test section

After the test section, the fluid is sent to the heat exchanger HX101 (SWEP B4THx20) in order to cool it back to its initial temperature and sent back to the accumulator. The cooling fluid in this case is water kept at constant temperature with the chiller CU101 (Van-der-Heijden VDH5000A). The chiller supplies water to the accumulator as well, to keep the fluid in liquid state at pressures below the critical point.

The test section is placed inside a closed and thermally insulated box, which can be tilted to different angles by means of swivel connectors attached to the main structure. In this way, identical fluid conditions can be tested with the same instrumentation at different flow orientations to study the parametric trends. Additionally, the test section was built separately from the main fluid conditioning loop so that different pieces of equipment (for instance dedicated heat exchangers designed to work with fluids in supercritical conditions) could be tested in the future. The current test section structure is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Side view of tiltable structure (left), view of the swivel connection (right).

Figure 7 shows the cycle in a p-h diagram, with the red lines covering a sub-critical operation and the light blue covering the supercritical operation. In this diagram, the dotted line corresponds to the accumulator operating line. Point 1 corresponds to an operating point in AC-101, point 2 is the outlet of LP-101, point 3 is the line downstream of EH-101 and point 4 the outlet of the test section.

Figure 7. p-h diagram of the test loop

The data acquisition system was built with National Instruments hardware. Software for data handling and process monitoring was developed in LabVIEW.

Figure 8. P&ID of the sCO₂ test rig.

2.4. TESTING PROGRAMME

Given the extensive gaps in knowledge in sCO₂ heating studies in small sized pipes, the amount of data to be measured and analyzed is significant and thus, the first phase of this study will focus on the effect of diameter at different pressures, with systematic results expected to be available by September 2025. The operating parameters to be investigated are summarized in Table 1. The conditions were chosen based on the available literature, summarized in the beginning of this section. The priority of the test campaign will be to fix correctly a constant inlet condition in terms of inlet pressure and temperature, thus ensuring consistent entry conditions.

Table 1. Operating conditions for the sCO₂ test setup.

ID (mm)	OD (mm)	Operating pressure (bar)	Inlet temperature (°C)	Outlet temperature (°C)	Mass flux (kg/m ² s)
1.0	1.59	76	20	40	1500
					1000
					500
		80	25	45	1500
					1000
					500
		85	30	50	1500
					1000
					500
2.15	3.18	76	20	40	1200
					800
					500
		80	25	45	1200
					800
					500
		85	30	50	1200
					800
					500

The results of this initial will be extensively discussed in the PhD thesis.

The investigation of mass flux effects in vertical up-flow and the detailed study of HTD will follow in the coming years as part of a broader analysis, ensuring a thorough assessment of the relevant parameters.

3. KRYPTON AS REFRIGERANT

3.1. COOLING SYSTEMS AT CERN AND FUTURE NEEDS

At the core of the Tracking detectors, the pixel modules are installed in the innermost layer providing a very precise spatial resolution and high signal-to-noise ratio [22]. Since the launch of the LHC [24], the silicon pixel sensors must be protected and preserved from the damage created by the high radiation levels in proximity of those detectors, to maintain their functionality and efficiency [23]. The goal of the dedicated cooling system is therefore not only to remove the heat produced by the detector on-board electronic, but also to maintain the sensors cold and at a controlled temperature, maximizing the signal to noise ratio.

In the old generations of particle detectors, single-phase water cooling in a sub-atmospheric system was used as the radiation level was sufficiently low [25]. However, with the advancement of the semiconductor technology and increase of the radiation dose, the high freezing point of water and its electrical conductivity pushed the need for novel technologies. The initial approach of using water-based mixture with freezing point depressant fluid as methanol was dropped in favour of single-phase of evaporative cooling systems using perfluorocarbons (respectively C₆F₁₄ and C₃F₈) for cooling of the sensors down to -20 °C, due to their dielectric properties, molecular stability and non-flammability [26, 27]. The first evaporative system was an oil-free compressor-based cooling cycle which suffered by fatigue problems on the compressors that caused frequent failures and leaks. In addition, a controlled cooldown of the sensors especially during critical transient as the startup was difficult to achieve, leading to an electric failure of many silicon modules and strongly reducing their lifetime due to the exposure to thermal shocks. As an alternative to the C₃F₈ compressor-based system, a gravity-driven C₃F₈ thermosiphon system was designed and launched in operation in 2015 [28] while the compressor-based cycle became the backup unit. However, at low evaporating temperatures, the poor thermal performance of the fluid concerning the low operating pressure made a new evaporating cooling solution with CO₂ gaining popularity until it was chosen as cooling solution in the cosmic particle detector AMS-02 [29,30] and in the LHCb Velo detector [31]. Afterwards also the ATLAS ITk (Inner Tracker), which is the innermost detector directly located around the interaction point where hardware minimization is even more demanding, adopted a CO₂ cooling-based solution. The diameter of the cooling channel with CO₂ could have been reduced by approximately a factor four, while maintaining acceptable temperature difference between inlet-outlet of each evaporative cooling line. The temperature budget, defined by a maximum allowable temperature difference of 3 K between the inlet and outlet, serves as a key specification for selecting the optimal design.

According to the High Luminosity plan (HL-LHC), a major upgrade of the entire underground infrastructure will take place in 2033-2034 [32]. Following periods of operation (Run), the LHC is stopped for one or more years during the so-called Long Shutdowns (LS) to carry out maintenance, consolidation, or a complete upgrade of each sub-detectors. The next two major upgrades (LS3 and LS4) will see the detectors interested by unprecedented level of high particle densities. Today's cooling system operating with CO₂ has reached its temperature limitation due to the triple point location, i.e., -56 degC. The 2PACL (two-phase accumulator pumped loop) is part of a cascade refrigeration system aimed to remove the heat released by the sensors. At detector level, the minimum temperature attainable is around -40°C, considering the subcooling required at the pump inlet and the increasing losses of the fluid while operating at low operating pressures [33,34]. As a result of such limitations, thermal runaway of the sensors most exposed to radiation levels is predicted for the future detector upgrade if no measures are taken.

For this reason, as part of a large study, a preliminary study on environmental-friendly refrigerants for operation temperature range below -50°C showed the noble gas krypton as potential candidate for

thermal management of future detectors, with the possibility to go as low as its triple point ($\approx -157^{\circ}\text{C}$) [35]. The main reason for its better thermal performance compared to other natural working fluids is the high operating pressure, which allows to reduce the size of the cooling channels meeting the demand for hardware minimization inside the detectors. A new ejector-supported system using krypton was developed [35] with extensive functionality to cope with the harsh detector requirements. The krypton system will be coupled with the existing CO₂ primary chiller, maintaining the cascade system fully environmentally friendly. A thermal design of the system was addressed, and guidelines for the future system's design were developed as this is crucial for the upcoming steps into the experimental verification of the cycle technology. Given the different fluid state of krypton under different temperatures levels for the range of interest (below -60°C), covering both supercritical and two-phase state, the system was designed considering flow boiling conditions in the detectors in the range $-70/-80^{\circ}\text{C}$, as the critical temperature of krypton is approximately -64°C . The idea was to design a flexible cycle that can be adapted to either single phase (down to approximately -60°C) or evaporative cooling detector technologies, by replacing the cooling channels inside the detector to fully exploit the different thermodynamic properties of the fluid while moving from one fluid state to another. In parallel, also the ejector that acts as pumping device will need to be designed accordingly for optimal behaviour.

3.2. KRYPTON SETUP

Figure 9 shows the schematic of the cycle and Figure 10 the pressure-enthalpy diagram of the fluid where the different consecutive transients encountered during operation are highlighted, which are discussed in detail in [35]. Differently than CO₂, krypton at room temperature is in gas phase requiring new cooling technology to grant protection against a possible thermal shock during the cycle startup and cooldown. The cycle resembles a typical ejector-driven compression system with some modifications regarding the constraints introduced by the detectors, such as passive components near the irradiated area. The system comprises a compression loop and a pumped loop. The compression loop includes the oil-free compressor, an external high-pressure tank to control the system pressure during single-phase operation (transients A-B-C, Figure 10), the gas cooling stage where the heat removed from the detectors and compressor is rejected to the first stage CO₂ chiller, a liquid receiver where the major charge of the system is stored and an internal heat exchanger to simultaneously ensure superheated gas at the compressor suction and extra subcooling at the ejector motive inlet to boost the cooling capacity. The pumped loop comprises the ejector and the distribution system to the detectors (heat exchanger, capillaries and cooling channels) which is very similar to what in use nowadays with the CO₂ technology, called 2PACL (Two-phase accumulator pumped loop). The ejector is a passive device that uses the expansion work available in the high pressure fluid coming from the compressor's discharge to pre-compress for free a secondary low pressure stream (blue, Figure 9) up to an intermediate pressure (black, Figure 9). Ejectors are static device that requires low maintenance but with poor ability of actively controlling the entrain flow in the low-pressure stage. For this reason, a needle-controlled ejector should be used to change the pumping capacity of the device adapting to the required flow conditions across the detectors. The modulation of the secondary flow occurs by changing the insertion position of the needle into the motive nozzle. For more details the reader can refer to [35].

Figure 9: simplified architecture of the krypton cooling system.

Figure 10: Pressure-enthalpy diagram of krypton with the four main transients encountered during operation highlighted with A-B-C-D.

An illustrative example of the working principle of the cycle under flow boiling conditions in the detector, is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: System layout of transcritical ejector krypton system (a) & representation in the p-h diagram (b). Numbers are used to help the reader identifying the working principle.

The superheated gas at the compressor suction (1) is compressed up to the required discharge pressure (2). The warm gas at the compressor outlet goes through a first gas cooling stage where its temperature is further reduced (3). Part of the flow is bypassed to the suction line via the bypass valve, acting as a capacity control regulator. The remaining high-pressure flow undergoes an additional cooling through the 2nd stage of gas cooling and the internal heat exchanger, which provides also safe levels of superheat at the compressor suction. The high-pressure stream (5) enters the motive nozzle where its pressure is reduced (6) creating locally a depressurization zone (9) that enables some flow to be entrained from the low-pressure stage. The two streams are then mixed in the mixing chamber (7) and then the flow is pre-compressed (8) via a divergent section called diffuser and discharge into the tank in the form of liquid-vapor mixture. At the detector level, flow circulation is promoted by the ejector recovering part of the expansion work available (5-6). The saturated liquid is partially bypassed while the remaining is subcooled in the concentric tube-in-tube heat exchanger, bringing the liquid to nearly the same temperature on the return line (12-16). Under high pressure close to the critical point, being the liquid phase slightly compressible, a mixing at the capillary inlet (13) is provided to ensure saturated conditions at the entrance of the detector after expansion through the capillary (13-14). The saturated liquid is vaporized inside the detector (14-15) to low vapor qualities, to prevent any risk of inception of dry-out. The exhaust two-phase flow (15) is further vaporized in the return line (15-16) before being sucked by ejector.

Two different section's view of the experimental prototype are illustrated in Figure 12. The new cycle technology was designed, built and commissioned in the Varmeteknisk laboratory at NTNU (Trondheim, Norway). Considering the absence of krypton-rated component in the market, as its use as refrigerant was not explored before, but with very similar operating pressures between CO₂ and krypton, there is potential to employ similar cooling constructions already available in the market. Concerning the compressor, an oil-lubricated machine was installed due to the lack of an oil-free machine in the market specifically designed for krypton-like properties, mainly high densities, but it will be only limited to the demonstrator built in the initial stage of the project.

Figure 12: Compressor and detector mockup box.

3.3. DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF THE EXPERIMENTAL PROTOTYPE

The prototype was designed using the simulation software Dymola and the TIL library offered by TLK-ThermoGmbH, specifically developed for thermal systems. The software tool was also used as virtual test bench to verify effectiveness of different control strategies to handle the transients presented in (A-B-C-D, Figure 10) while guaranteeing a precise temperature control at the detector level. Considering the extremely low mass of the detectors, a precise control of the fluid temperature entering the cooling channels is the best method to control the cooldown of the detectors and the surrounding structure, as it has to align with the fluid temperature (after some time delay given by the time constant of the system).

The preliminary test campaign was carried out at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), where cold tests were limited by the lack of a powerful cold chiller (CO₂ primary chiller). Furthermore, in the initial stage the external high-pressure tank to control the system charge was not present yet. The system was initially commissioned and tested with CO₂ before transitioning to the new proposed refrigerant. The experimental campaign with the proposed coolant (krypton) was planned as follows:

- Oil-refrigerant gas solubility: the first concern related to the interaction of krypton gas with standard lubricant oil (PAG68) developed for CO₂ was tested at NTNU.
- Ejector dimensioning: the ejector is a vital component in the cycle as it allows gas/liquid krypton circulation through the detector loop. As its performance and entrained flow in the low-pressure side (detector) are highly dependent on the geometry and thermodynamic

conditions at the motive inlet (high-pressure inlet side), different ejectors should be installed in parallel such that they can be switched on depending on the operating conditions (A-B-C-D).

- Testing of technical limitation of the existing CO₂ high-pressure compressor installed in the test-rig with respect to the higher mass flows demanded with krypton compared to a CO₂ application
- Testing of the proposed control strategy initially verified in the simulation tool with experimental data
- Comparison of the experimental data with the simulation tool to verify system transients and accuracy of the numerical model in order to build a flexible and reliable tool for future developments.

3.4. RESULTS

The solubility of krypton gas into the oil PAG68 was initially verified to address the behaviour of the new proposed refrigerant with a standard lubricant. Even though the standard ASHRAE 97/07(RA2017) was not followed rigorously, the test was carried out in a temperature control environment to have a meaningful estimation of the pressure decay over time of the mixture krypton-oil. High solubilities typical of hydrocarbons have been identified when using krypton, meaning that oil properties will be dominated by refrigerant properties and some krypton charge will be lost in the oil, requiring additional refilling of the unit. Figure 13 shows the gas bubbles dissolved in the oil when flashing the mixture out of the pressurized tank.

Figure 13: Krypton gas bubbles dissolved in the oil during the solubility test.

Secondly, a dedicated dynamic model of the setup was used to obtain the necessary boundary conditions to design the geometry of the gas ejector dedicated to the phase A-B (Figure 10). This ejector was built, installed and tested in the demonstrator unit. In Figure 14 the three main parts of the gas ejector are shown, namely motive nozzle, mixing chamber and diffuser. Through the motive nozzle the high-pressure stream is expanded, and part of the work is recovered in the form of compressing a lower-pressure suction flow. The suction flow enters the mixing chamber where it exchanges mass and heat with the primary flow. Along the diffuser, a divergent conical shape converts part of the kinetic energy into a pressure increase.

Figure 14: Gas ejector designed, view of the three main parts dismounted.

The reciprocating compressor was tested to evaluate possible technical limitations mainly related to the higher densities experienced with krypton at the suction port. It was found that the compressor is able to compress the krypton at different suction gas temperature, ranging from 20 °C down to -60°C under different pressure ratio. However, a higher density than 200 kg/m³, which is already above the maximum CO₂ gas density normally encountered in a commercial CO₂ chiller, was found to introduce excessive mechanical stress on the valve plates at the compressor suction. Further tests will be carried out to define this technical limitation in order to install new valve plates that can withstand the densities registered in supercritical and two-phase area (phase C-D, Figure 10).

The startup and subsequent cooldown process to gently bring the detectors from room temperature to the cold temperatures have been tested. The results are illustrated in Figure 15, focusing on the temperature stability of the fluid entering the detector section when the compressor starts (a-b) and the cooldown speed starting from approximately 20°C down to -50°C (c). During the compressor startup, the fluid at the detector level remains thermally unaltered with no risk of thermal shocks. A cooldown of approximately 70 K was achieved over approximately 150 minutes, with an average of 2 K/min. This demonstrates the capability of the cycle to go as slow as required with the possibility of boosting the cooling speed via a change of the pumping capacity provided by the ejector (mainly by an increase of the motive inlet pressure).

Figure 15: Temperature stability at the detector level (a) during compressor startup (b). Cooldown rate from room temperature down to -50°C in approximately two and half hour (c), with an average of 2 K/min.

3.5. FUTURE WORK

The system has currently been moved to CERN where a connection to a cold and powerful CO₂ chiller is possible, to test the transient C-D (Figure 10) and to prove the concept of an environmentally friendly cascade system with CO₂-krypton. The high-pressure tank will also be available at the end of March, enabling testing at high-pressures and transition from supercritical to two-phase operation (C to D).

The next test campaign will comprise:

- Analysis of the experimental data concerning the gas ejector and comparison with numerical model to refine the tool used for the design, as the ejector is a vital component in the system and an accurate model is crucial to obtain a performant ejector
- Startup of the system at the design pressure thanks to the charge control provided by the external high-pressure tank
- Entire cooldown down to -60°C at high-pressures (A-B)
- Manufacturing of a new ejector specifically designed for the supercritical phase

- Investigation of the supercritical cycle (phase C), both with unpowered and powered test sections to investigate the response and the controllability of the cycle in the supercritical area.

4. FUTURE PLANS

With the new setup dedicated to precision measurements of sCO₂ properties, new experimental results covering the main open points from the published scientific literature will be submitted for publication and extensively discussed in the PhD thesis, foreseen for completion in September 2025. This activity will also produce systematic data on the thermal-fluidic properties of fluids in supercritical state at reduced pressures in the order of 1.2, very useful for the optimization of the components of the innovative Kr refrigeration cycle operating in that area: the gas coolers, the internal heat exchanger and the ejector.

The setup dedicated to the study of the krypton cycle, now moved from NTNU to CERN, is now connected to a CO₂ transcritical primary plant able to provide stable evaporation in the heat exchanger at -53 °C. This will allow to explore the full operational envelope of the designed cycle. Also in this case the results will be submitted for publication and the whole work will be extensively discussed in the PhD thesis foreseen for completion before the end of the year.

Both activities will then be continued at CERN and NTNU over a pluriannual programme of experimental campaigns and data analysis targeting a consolidation of the technologies and readiness for application in future detectors by the end of the 3rd Long Shut Down of LHC (LS3).

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ANNEX1: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ID	Inner Diameter
OD	Outer Diameter
h_b	Specific enthalpy of the bulk fluid
h_{in}	Specific enthalpy at the inlet of the test section
h_{m1}	(explained in the text, see page 7/30)
HTC	Heat Transfer Coefficient
HTD	Heat Transfer Deterioration